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TECHNOLOGY
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODELS FOR ESTIMATING
EVAPOTRANSPIRATION

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ABSTRACT

Evapotranspiration (ETo) is a complex, dynamic and non-linear hydrological process. Accurate estimation of ETo has long been an eminent topic of interest in the research community for its importance in effective planning and sustainable water resource management. Although the FAO-56 Penman-Monteith (PM) equation has been accepted as a standard equation for ETo measurement, the primary concern that inhibits the applicability of this equation is the requirement for all the climatological variables, which might not be available at a given location. Owing to the remarkable success and accuracy achieved by Artificial Intelligence (AI) in almost every sphere, scientists have proposed the usage AI models for ETo prediction as an alternate to the conventional methods. The artificial intelligence approach emerges as the best possible solution to map the relationships between climatic parameters and ET, even with limited knowledge of the interactions between variables. The results from the publications published over the last few years for ETo prediction using AI under varied agro-climatic scenarios have been analysed and synthesized. The advantages and disadvantages of the established AI techniques have been discussed in each subsection. The characteristics of the basic artificial intelligence models are also explored in this paper. Some of the derived insights and major findings are discussed. A research vision for the novice researchers in the applicability of the aforementioned techniques, in context of ETo prediction, but also be helpful as a compilation of the AI modelling studies for ETo prediction for the established water resource engineers and hydrologists.

Keywords: Evapotranspiration, ETo prediction, FAO-56PM equation, agro-climatic scenarios, artificial intelligence models for estimation etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Managing irrigation systems in arid and semiarid climates is a difficult task owing to the limited availability of water resources and overexploitation of the existing ones. The combined loss of water through evaporation from the soil surface and transpiration from the plant surface is jointly referred to as a single term called Evapotranspiration (ET). ET is the principal component of the hydrological cycle, and its precise estimation plays a key role in various studies such as hydrologic water balance, rainfall-runoff modelling, agrometeorology, irrigation scheduling, water budgeting, planning and management of water resources and ecosystem modeling. As evapotranspiration plays a vital role in determining crop water requirement, accurate measurement of evapotranspiration becomes evident. Normally lysimeters are used for direct measurement of evapotranspiration. However, high operating costs and the need for accurate measurements has limited the use of lysimeters. In nineteenth century, researchers developed various physical, empirical and semi-empirical equations that used meteorological variables to estimate reference crop evapotranspiration (ETo). The Food and Agricultural Organization of United Nations (FAO) has accepted the FAO Penman-Monteith (FAO-56PM) as the standard equation to estimate ETo (Allen *et al.* 1998). Large requirement of climatic variables has limited the use of FAO-56PM equation in developing countries like India, where, availability of these records has often been minimal. Additionally, the performance of empirical equations using fewer climatic variables is often found to be inconsistent when tested under different climatic conditions (Nandagiri and Koor 2006; Tabari *et al.* 2011; Shiri *et al.* 2014).

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[1]

In the recent years, use of artificial intelligence (AI) techniques like artificial neural networks (ANN), adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS) and least square support vector machine (LS-SVM) for modeling intricate hydrological processes has increased significantly (Sudheer, et al. 2003; Kumar et al. 2008; Chauhan and Shrivastava 2009; Kişi and Çimen 2009; Kişi 2009, 2013; Kumar et al. 2010; Cobaner 2011; Tabari et al. 2012; Wen et al. 2015). Also, few studies were carried out regarding ETo estimation using various AI techniques (Tabari and Talaei 2013; Kisi and Cengiz 2013).

The existing literature reveals that ETo, like many other hydrological processes operate under a large range of scales varying from one hour to several months leading to non-linear and non-stationary behavior of dataset. AI models alone may not be able to cope with these characteristics of the dataset if input and/or output data are not preprocessed. Wavelet pre-processed data may increase the efficiency of an AI model by providing useful information about original dataset on various resolution levels as appeared in recent studies (Wang and Luo 2008; Deka and Prahlada 2012). Furthermore, there is also a need for working towards enhancing the performance of these models using hybridization.

2. OBJECTIVE:

To study the performance of AI models following objectives are designed.

1. Development of hybrid models combining wavelet transform and AI model to estimate daily and weekly ETo in semi-arid regions of India.
2. Performance evaluation of developed hybrid models to select the best model with reference to FAO-56PM for estimating ETo.

3. METHODOLOGY:

This section includes the selection procedure of inputs for the AI models. Further, the data pre-processing technique, discrete wavelet transform (DWT) is described. A short introduction to ANN, ANFIS and LS-SVM is also included.

4. STUDY AREA

The data will be collected from IMD Pune for western Maharashtra region. The data sourced will include maximum air temperature [T_{max} (°C)], minimum air temperature [T_{min} (°C)], maximum relative humidity [RH_{min} (%)], minimum relative humidity in percentage [RH_{min} (%)], sunshine duration (hours) and wind speed [U_2 (m/sec)]. This data will be used for testing and validation of the AI models

Artificial neural network

ANN an information processing system stimulates the ability of a human brain to sort out patterns and learn from trial and error. It has the ability to extract relationships that exist within the data. Typically, ANN architecture consists of a series of processing elements called neurons. Neurons are arranged in layers which are fully connected to the next layer by interconnection weights. Weights are first randomly assigned to all of the connections in the network. These initial values of weights are then corrected during a training (learning) process. In the training process, estimated outputs are compared to the known outputs, and the errors occurred are back propagated to obtain the appropriate weight adjustments necessary in minimizing the errors.

Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system

Jang (1993) proposed a method that used neural network learning algorithm for constructing a set of fuzzy if-then rules from stipulated input output pairs. Fundamentally, ANFIS is a functional equivalent of fuzzy interface systems, endowed with neural learning capabilities. An ANFIS model combines the transparent and linguistic representation of a fuzzy system with learning ability of ANN.

Least square support vector machine

The foundation of support vector machines (SVM) has been developed by Vapnik (1995) and is gaining popularity due to many attractive features and promising empirical performances. The formulation embodies Structural Risk Minimization (SRM) principle, which has shown better performances than the Empirical Risk Minimization principle (ERM), employed by conventional neural networks. SRM minimizes an upper bound on

the expected risk, as opposed to ERM that minimizes the error on the training data. It is this difference, which equips SVM with a greater ability to generalize, thus, achieving the goal of statistical learning. LS-SVM is a reformulation of the principles of SVM, which involves equality instead of inequality constraints.

Wavelet transform

Wavelet Transform decomposes original time series into wavelet subseries of different resolution in the time domain. Wavelet pre-processed data may increase the efficiency of an AI model by providing useful information about original data set on various resolution levels. The choice of mother wavelet depends on the data to be analyzed. The datasets will be examined and suitable mother wavelets will be tested.

Flowchart

Figure 1 represents the flowchart of the methodology adopted for selecting the best model

Figure 1: Flowchart of the methodology that will be adopted

Artificial Intelligence Models

4.1 Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

Artificial neural network (ANN), as suggested by the name, is a variation of the machine learning model that resembles the neural network of human brain. In the latter, neurons are connected to each other via synapses. In ANN, synapses are replaced by weights and biases connections. This helps to map the relationship between inputs and outputs. A Multilayer perceptron (MLP) is one of the earliest types of ANN, and it was introduced by Rosenblatt. However, it was not until the year 1989 that MLP was proven to be able to approximate functions after training. In 1992, in tandem with the advancement of computer development, the MLP showed better performance than traditional statistical method for the first time.

The application of the MLP in estimation of ET_0 was initiated by Kumar *et al.* [47]. In the study, the authors collected the six essential parameters for estimating ET_0 using the PM model in Davis, California. This set of data was dated from 1 January 1990 to 30 June 2000. At the same time, a second set of data dated from 1 January 1960 to 31 December 1963 was obtained together with their corresponding lysimeter readings. The authors intended to compare the performance of the MLP with different architecture trained with different target data. The outcome of the study showed that, when all the six parameters were fed as input of the MLP model, a single layer of seven hidden neurons with 5000 learning cycles was ample to represent the nonlinear process of ET. The training of the model using lysimeter measurement as target produced slightly more accurate estimations than using the PM model. This not only justified the ability of the MLP to map inputs to output in

the absence of clear relationship, but also at the same time laid down a foundation that estimation of the PM model is sufficiently good to be used as a target for the model training.

4.2. Support Vector Machine (SVM)

The support vector machine (SVM) is another popular algorithm used in machine learning modeling, especially when it is claimed to be powerful and robust in regression and classification tasks. Cortes and Vapnik laid down the basic and foundation of the current SVM model. Instead of involving large number of neurons and iterations to infer the relationship between inputs and outputs, the SVM plots the datasets into a feature space. The relationship between inputs and outputs is predicted using kernel function, where problem complexity and accuracy can be optimized concurrently.

Since the ET_0 prediction is more likely a regression problem rather than a classification problem, a variation of the SVM, which is the support vector regression (SVR), is normally used. In the SVR, a loss function is used to define the deviation allowance as well as the function to approximate the targeted output. The working principle of SVM is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Working principle of support vector machine.

According to Raghavendra and Deka, the SVM was widely used in hydrology application, including the estimation of ET_0 . The advantages and strengths of the SVM include high robustness, capability to solve complex problems, less susceptible to over fitting, and it can provide a compact description of the model. The network structure of the SVM is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Network structure of support vector machine

The utilization of the SVM in predicting ET_0 with ground observation data started as early as 2010. The predictions of the SVM were compared with the CIMIS Penman, HS model, Ritchie model, and the Turc model. The authors discovered that when all climatic parameters were available, the SVM outperformed all other models in all the stations studied. When wind speed and relative humidity were removed during the training of the SVM, the model underestimated ET_0 but still had satisfying outcomes, whereby it only performed slightly worse than conventional the HS model. In fact, the authors also claimed that the SVM had better performance than the ANN, where the former incurred lower error and higher correlation with the standard PM model.

4.3. Fuzzy Models

Fuzzy logic allows the description of data in such a way that a “degree of likeliness” can be given. In other words, by using fuzzy logic, instead of describing in terms of “either A or B”, one can produce a membership degree between 0 and 1 so that the description looks like “partly A and partly B”. Application of fuzzy logic requires an initial set up by experts to determine the type of distribution by selecting a membership function. In addition, three major ingredients should be fed to fuzzy inference system (FIS), namely a set of fuzzy rule base, database which contains the membership functions and a mechanism (either Sugeno or Mamdani) to apply the fuzzy rules on input and output. The main difference between Sugeno and Mamdani fuzzy logic is the approach to compute the final output. The overall flow of an FIS is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Overall flow of fuzzy inference system

The history of applying fuzzy logic to estimate ET_0 began in 2009. Keskin et al. forecasted the pan evaporation of Lake Eğirdir in Turkey using ground observation climatic data. A comparable study was done in Karso watershed of India. The authors did not only study the feasibility of fuzzy logic predicting pan evaporation, but also the performance of fuzzy logic as compared to the ANN, the least-squared SVR and the adaptive-neuro fuzzy inference system (ANFIS), was also evaluated. The authors remarked that the fuzzy logic model emerged as one of the best models for pan evaporation estimation. This study stressed the importance of fuzzy rules in producing good estimations. Successful application of fuzzy logic shall have good membership functions as foundation. The tuning of membership function not only requires expert knowledge, but is also time-consuming, especially for a complex phenomenon like ET that can be affected by a number of parameters. Hence, the ANN acts as a complimentary to the fuzzy logic to form an ANFIS. Application of the ANFIS for ET_0 estimation was first done by Kisi and Öztürk and there are a number of recent works showing promising results

4.4. Tree Based Models

Breiman was the first person to compile decision trees into two main categories, which were the classification tree and regression tree. However, it was Quinlan who provided a better understanding on the operation of tree models. In Quinlan’s work, it was stated that the decision would continue to split and grow as long as the data within the nodes of the trees were still considered as impure. In the case of ET, using a tree model for regression analysis is favored over classification. Within this context, Pal and Deswal introduced a widely accepted splitting criterion for the M5 tree model. They claimed that, in order to produce better splits with highest computation efficiency, data within any nodes should be split in such a way that the standard deviation reduction could be maximized. It was observed that the M5 tree model could produce high correlation results to the ET_0 value, although the errors of estimations gradually increased when input climatic parameters were reduced.

There are several research works published that followed up the study of Pal and Deswal. Rahimikhoob et al. attempted to convert pan evaporation data in ET_0 while using other climatic parameters as complementary data. Subsequently, the performance of M5 tree model in predicting ET_0 was compared with the ANN. The study was done in Iran where wind speed and radiation data were found to be absent. The author concluded that, under such circumstances, the M5 tree model could achieve similar performance to the ANN. It was also suggested that the M5 tree model should be favored over the ANN due to its simplicity in terms of computation.

According to the papers reviewed regarding to tree-based modeling, it is clear to us that tree-based models exhibit a clear advantage of simple and fast computation. In spite of that, the pitfall of such a model is also obvious. As the tree in the model would have to grow until there are no any other possible splits (the data is deemed to be pure by then), there is a risk of overgrowing the tree. In such circumstance, over fitting could occur which is undesirable for regression analysis. To overcome the problem, a strategy known as pruning is needed to remove unnecessary parts of the tree and replaced them with linear functions. Moreover, the sequence

of tree's splitting could end up with different results even though with the same set of training data. To compensate the effect of randomness, trees are sometimes bundled to form a random forest. This will be discussed in detail in later parts of this review.

Basic artificial intelligence models have their own advantages as well as disadvantages. The ANN can be efficient in fitting nonlinear relationship, but it is less explanatory and prone to overfit. The SVM has good generalizability at the expense of costly computation especially for high dimensionality problems. The fuzzy logic provides interpretable rules but that would require initial set up with expert knowledge. The Tree models are computationally efficient, however, would incur high errors. Hence, using basic artificial intelligence models alone is insufficient to accommodate the increasing expectations of their performances. In the following next section, different hybridization techniques of artificial intelligence models are explored as an effective solution to overcome the problems encountered above.

5. CONCLUSION:

The estimation of ET is of paramount importance, especially when dealing with agricultural activities. This review has outlined the pitfalls of conventional models based on energy balance which included the high dependency on climatic parameters. In addition, empirical models could be specific to certain regions and this in turn requires further calibration before the models could be used. Emergence of artificial intelligence models, which operated on the premise of a black-box principle aims to overcome these problems. The integration of artificial intelligence reignites the possibility of reduction of the now much needed climatic parameters for estimation of ET. Since artificial intelligence models are data-driven, this review has pointed out some sources of data, and also the significance of different parameters in various climate patterns. ANN, SVM, fuzzy models, and tree-based models had been studied extensively in the past and their feasibilities were tried and tested. Nevertheless, studies had revealed that, in the case of limited meteorological parameters or data, performance of these artificial intelligence models would deteriorate.

In view of such circumstance, data fusion techniques had been developed as a solution. Bootstrap aggregating is useful when available data size is too little to train a good model. Bayesian modelling approaches rely on the imputation of posterior probabilities to weigh the correctness of individual models. The boosting algorithm works by combining several weak learners to form a strong learner. Data decomposition has distinct characteristics whereby it extracts useful information at different resolutions via certain forms of transformation. This could assist in the removal of unwanted noise prior analysis. The purpose of performing data decomposition, especially wavelet transformation is to draw certain trends from historical data in order to predict future behaviour of ET. This could serve as a guideline in terms of parameters selections and ensemble strategies for future research workers who wish to have a fresh start on ET estimation using the hybrid artificial intelligence models.

Besides providing the chronological development and guidelines to select methods or algorithms for ET estimation using artificial intelligence models, this review also suggested the future trends of the development of artificial intelligence in ET prediction. In upcoming studies, it is anticipated that data fusion or assimilation would be the major subject alongside with the development of more robust artificial intelligence models. It is in our interest that ground observation data can be merged with remote sensing data. New hybrid models are also anticipated in order to increase the prediction accuracy and speed. In the near future, climate change will be a major environmental issue and researchers shall be cautious about its effect. With matured and well-developed models, we could expect that more parameters well associated with ET can be explored to discover their relationship with ET, all in all for a more profound understand of the processes. Finally, forecasting horizons are to be lengthened for achieving water resources allocation with higher efficiency. It can be a useful tool during key steps of the decision-making process for policy makers, especially in water resources management for a successful economic growth and development in the agricultural sector.

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[6]

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